

Study of mathematical cartoons as auxiliary teaching materials and students' experience of flow

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ABSTRACT

Learning mathematics is conducive to equilibrium of the left and right brain and thus to the brain's overall development. However, some consider mathematics tedious, and resist learning it. In this study, two female students were asked to serve as research assistants. Although both were proficient at drawing cartoons, they had mid- or low-level mathematics performance, and therefore were tasked to draw cartoons explaining mathematical units. The experience of flow in their cartoons indicated that a combination of their interest in cartoon-drawing and mathematics combined with discussions with a mathematics teacher could reduce their resistance to learning mathematics and thereby improve their understanding of the significance of applied mathematics in daily life. This study thus enhanced the independent mathematical thinking abilities of its participants and stimulated their higher-level mathematical thinking using cartoons as auxiliary teaching materials. This study comprised interviews the two students to seek an explanation for the context of enhancing mathematical thinking abilities.

Keywords: auxiliary teaching material, experience of flow, mathematical cartoon, mathematical thinking abilities

1. INTRODUCTION

Learning mathematics favors balanced development of the left and right brain (George et al., 2021). Mathematics is vital to human life, and those who do not reject it consider it beautiful, necessary, and elegant and maintain a positive, commendatory view of it. However, many students resist learning mathematics, stating that they are not interested in it. In fact, learning mathematics is not only conducive to the development of logical thinking but also enhances creativity, appreciation of beauty, and intuition.

Cartoons are considered a popular art (Mou, 2000), particularly in Japan and Europe, where they are regarded as the ninth major art form, following cinema (Fan, 1996). Cartoons attract many viewers at different levels, and they have been developed into a type of popular culture. At the Taiwanese Cartoon History Exhibition, Kuang-nan Huang stated that cartoons had become an irresistible trend, finding applications in science and the arts without national boundaries. He also noted that this symbolic language had become a major force in social communication (National Museum of History, 2000) and that cartoons could become a force to change social values. According to one study (Arif Mansur et al., 2003), the educational effect of cartoons is firmly established, and the author was thus deeply troubled by public attitudes regarding cartoons. In the context of multimedia development, cartoons are

considered only as a type of communication media. The author thus argued that nonanimated cartoons are preferable for use as learning tools. Parents should therefore encourage their children to read cartoons when they are in primary school, because during this period children have a better ability to think in images. The right type of cartoons can enhance children's interest and learning effectiveness, and therefore parents should act as a filter to help children choose suitable cartoons. Image-based instructions could help to lay a foundation for textual thinking and cultivate lively, proactive character traits, because cartoons are widely accepted for their inherent humor, wit, and versatility, thereby attracting readers from all walks of life (National Museum of History, 2000). The research results of Feler and Brain (2020) also show that 70% of students believe that comics help learning and memory. To this end, the present study aimed to produce cartoon teaching materials for classroom instruction. Mathematics teachers planned and reviewed the cartoon contents and integrated elements of daily life into the teaching materials they provided to students. After using auxiliary teaching materials featuring mathematical cartoons, students' interest and learning effectiveness was enhanced.

2. STUDY AIMS

Against a diversified contemporary social background, and by means of advanced digital information technology, teaching materials have developed in a highly varied manner. Artistic and cultural elements have been integrated into contemporary education to cultivate students' thinking and interpreting abilities. Students can proactively acquire valuable knowledge through art, which helps them to better understand course content.

Douglas C Youvan (2023) noted that art and mathematics both have rich and universal significance as well as profound correlation. Today, mathematics remains a means for creative artists to convey ideas and find inspiration. Artists have adopted mathematics to enter the mindset of multidimensional space. Indeed, many artists have engaged in art-related mathematical concepts such as nonperiodic tiling, multidimensional spaces, and computer reproduction technology.

This study sought to produce mathematical cartoon teaching materials for real-life applications. These were created by two selected female students, A and B, who had no interest in mathematics and poor mathematical performance but were avid drawers of cartoons. This study provided an experimental task, observed the task processes and interviewed, explored their experiences of flow, and examined how their understandings and applications of mathematics were enhanced. It thus achieved two specific research aims:

- (1) Established the context of student experience.
- (2) Explored reasons to explain why enhancing mathematical thinking abilities.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Experience of flow

A balance between the challenges of an environment and a person's own skills is referred to as flow (Trevino & Webster, 1992). Because of different perceptions, personal traits, and environmental influences, people employ different skills to respond to such challenges. Csikszentmihalyi (1999) proposed that flow is the positive and subjective experience of a person during an activity, resulting in

the satisfaction of self-realization and a sense of happiness.

The research shows that academic self-efficacy is an important bridge between learning motivation and learning performance, and academic self-efficacy and flow experience play a mediating role between learning motivation and online learning performance (Tianyi et al., 2023). Therefore, teachers should formulate class instructions and create learning scenarios that enhance students' flow (Challco et al., 2016).

Flow represents an individual's "positive experience" (Hou, 2009). Tseng (2010) explored various methods of enhancing children's experience through flow, noting that flow is thus closely related to human perception. When experiencing flow, individuals choose increasingly difficult paths, a type of psychological selection that enhances the uniqueness and completeness of an experience. Huang (2014) recalled how flow resulted in the evolution of skills such as basic sketch and creative expression during artistic creation, as well as visual design, communication, image processing, and animation. By challenging oneself and improving skills, the frequency of flow experiences increases. Artistic creation can be used to eliminate negative emotions or transform such emotions into positive ones, leading to emotional adjustment. Therefore, a recuperative effect arises from emotional transformation through artistic creation, which may thus be viewed as a process of learning and self-healing.

Empirical studies have found that digital entertainment-based learning enhances learner performance for cognition, emotion, and skills (Prensky, 2001; Margoudi et al., 2016; Raziūnaitė et al., 2018; Wang & Yu, 2020). Noting that edutainment had become an effective teaching strategy and tool. The experience of flow thus has a considerable effect on learning. Considering the aforementioned work, the present study tasked its participants to apply their drawing skills to challenging mathematical units for which they had had poor results. Regarding the experience of flow, this study explored whether the participants' entertaining mathematical cartoon designs could enhance their satisfaction and self-realization and improve their experience of cartoon-drawing, as well as whether they would accept the challenge of learning higher-level mathematics in the future.

3.2 Mathematics cartoons

Shumura et al. (2012) examined the effect of storyline in cartoons on the memorization of mathematical knowledge and explored various methods for learning mathematics, including mathematical articles, cartoons, and stories. Participants who read stories were found to have improved mathematical performance, compared with those who used mathematical cartoons. However, the performance of mathematical cartoon users was similar, and also slightly higher than that of participants who read mathematical articles. Overall, the literature review indicated that mathematical performance was improved by cartoons, stories, and articles (ranked from high to low). These results indicate that using cartoons for learning mathematics is helpful.

The Mathematical Girls won an award from the Mathematical Society of Japan in 2014 for producing a mathematical cartoon series based on the books of Hiroshi (2007), which relate to mathematics and program design. This series has been translated into English, Chinese (both simplified and traditional), and Korean. The Mathematical Girls provided detailed explanations of mathematical theorems in a cartoon series comprising five episodes published from 2007 to 2012. The contents include the four primary school operations, real number lines, sequence and series, the Pythagorean theorem,

linear equations, quadratic equations with one variable, junior high school–level plane geometry, set theory, analytical geometry, inequality, trigonometric functions, permutation and composition, senior high school–level probability, university-level calculus, linear algebra, number theory, and abstract algebra. The series incorporates equations through dialogue and text to attract the interest of readers in learning and discussing mathematics.

According to the aforementioned studies, students reading and studying mathematical teaching materials using stories understand mathematics better than those who only read general mathematics articles. Japan has achieved favorable results in teaching mathematical equations through cartoon dialogues. Therefore, this study aimed to combine the popular cartoon format with the difficult, stressful subject of mathematics to produce mathematical cartoons. It thereby explored the degree of acceptance of mathematics and the effect of the experience of flow on students with poor mathematical performance after drawing mathematical cartoons.

4. RESEARCH METHOD

The two undergraduate assistants, Students A and B, had no interest in mathematics and poor mathematical performance in senior high school. This study required them to refer to the mathematical formulas in their textbooks and produce cartoons with the relevant content under the guidance of the authors. The study duration was 2 months. On Mondays, the participants discussed the contents of their mathematical cartoons with their teachers and made the necessary corrections.

This study employed an interview survey with a semi-open design. Interview survey is a qualitative method aiming to engage in communication with participants to gain deep insights from their perspectives and experiences. Interviews, often semi-structured or unstructured, may include individual or group settings. The essence of this research lies in understanding participants' views, exploring complex issues, building interpersonal rapport, and generating or modifying theories based on their insights (Seidman, 2006; Tracy, 2019; Ruslin, et. al., 2022).

The outline of which was as follows: 1) flow; 2) steps in composing the cartoons; 3) integrating mathematics in the style of cartoons (e.g., relationships among figures, objects, and mathematics); 4) combining animation with mathematical principles (ideas) and applying mathematics to life; 5) using group discussions about content to achieve inspiration and flow; 6) modifying (adding) cartoon content according to teachers' suggestions and defining moods during the process; 7) scheduling drawing time (time management); 8) changes in understanding of mathematics; 9) previous mathematical performance; and 10) most and least favorite parts of mathematics.

The study procedure was as follows:

- (1) Selecting participants.
- (2) Designing outlines.
- (3) Discussing with experts.
- (4) Conducting interviews.
- (5) Completing interviews.
- (6) Outputting results.

The outlines were discussed with experts in the field to ensure reliability and validity.

Interviews and semi-open questions were employed to conduct in-depth communication with the two students, whose replies were recorded.

5. RESEARCH RESULTS

After 2 months of discussion and production, the two participants' experiences of flow in drawing mathematical cartoons were as follows (Table 1).

Table 1. Experiences of flow during mathematical cartoon production

Questions	Student A	Student B
1. Flow.	Being asked to draw cartoons, I felt frightened, because my mathematical performance had been poor since childhood. It seemed weird that I should draw mathematical cartoons. But, this was a rare opportunity, and I wanted to challenge myself.	At first, I wanted to give up because of I felt that the workload assigned by my teacher was too heavy. After expressing my ideas, my teacher assigned me tasks that I was able to do. I was happy to be engaged in this task, and though I was extremely confused about calculus at first, as long as I thought that I could contribute to academic research in Taiwan, all the difficulties and hardships seemed worth it.
2. Steps in composing the cartoons.	At first, based on the information provided by my teacher, I knew that calculus was related to functions, so I started to draw function graphs. I came up with wave, swing, and bounce patterns, but they had restrictions in the demonstration, so I gave up on them. Finally, I came up with the idea of using sliding motion to express ideas, which had great potential for modification.	First, I needed to fully understand the concept of calculus, as expressed by the units. Next, I thought constantly about circumstances in which this concept might be applied, and tried to make the scenarios interesting. The cartoon started with a simple greeting to allow readers to let go of their resistance toward calculus. Then, I gradually introduced the concepts and formulas of calculus and explained them in detail. The cartoon figures would ask simple calculation questions to check if readers had understood the course.
3. How did you integrate mathematics in the	The main content related to mathematics in the cartoon was the skateboards. There were two	In terms of the figures, we introduced good qualities (such as being attractive, smart, lively, and

<p>style of cartoons (e.g., relationships among figures, objects, and mathematics)?</p>	<p>groups of main characters, one made up of senior middle-school students who went skateboarding and the other made up of undergraduates who constructed the skateboards. The undergraduates explained how they used mathematical equations to calculate the maximum and minimum values for skateboarding. The equations used in their blueprint were derived from calculus.</p>	<p>extroverted) to attract readers and indirectly link the images with mathematics. People might think that if they learn calculus well, they could be as smart and popular as the cartoon characters.</p>
<p>4. How did you combine animation with mathematical principles (ideas) and apply mathematics to life?</p>	<p>First, we thought about the question of mathematical applications to see if they could be related to life, or whether mathematical questions were related to life or other topics. Basically, we thought about how to apply mathematical principles to everyday life.</p>	<p>We learned mathematical principles through discussion and came up with some scenarios. To understand the mathematical principles and their applications, we borrowed books from the library and presented the content in the cartoons.</p>
<p>5. How did you use group discussions about content to achieve inspiration and flow?</p>	<p>Very nervous; I did not know if my idea would be accepted. But we share opinion each other, I add the well idea to improve my ideas.</p>	<p>Everyone on the team is really great. When I had questions, they would enthusiastically give advice. Through teamwork, the weak points of each member were compensated. We improved each other through cooperation. By sharing with one another, I was able to improve my original ideas.</p>
<p>6. How did you modify (add) cartoon content according to teachers' suggestions, and what moods did you experience during the process?</p>	<p>It depended on the content. If it was related to professional knowledge, I would modify it directly. If it was about the conflicting content in the figures, I might need to think up another plot. I felt assured. Because I did not have much professional knowledge, it was certainly nice if</p>	<p>I am not good at mathematics, so I discussed it with Mr. Hsu (my mathematics teacher) and then modified the cartoons. After each discussion, my mind was heavy with anxiety about the many tasks that had not been completed. But I also looked forward to presenting the final version of the cartoon.</p>

	someone could point out errors or ambiguities for correction or modification.	
7. How did you schedule your drawing time? (Time management)	I drew anytime I wanted. But if I had no time to draw, I would think about how to develop the plot.	At first my teacher and I had discussions on Friday afternoons. After Mr. Hsu joined our team, we chose Monday evenings, which was convenient for all of us. After our discussions, I would form a prototype in my mind and think about how to compose it and design the dialogues. I drew after I got off work, before or after classes, or before bed.
8. How did your understanding of mathematics change?	I gained a better understanding of the mathematics by practices, such as Extreme, slope, and derivative.	I gained a better understanding of the basic theorems of calculus and the differences between Newton and Leibniz through this task.
9. How was your previous mathematical performance?	Very poor. I always needed other students to help me.	Not good. I refused to learn mathematics. In any case, I did not use it.
10. Which is your most and least favorite part of mathematics?	Basically, I hate mathematics on the whole, but I enjoyed it when I learned a mathematical formula. I think my biggest difficulty in learning mathematics is actually flexibly applying different formulas.	I hate all the complicated formulas, and I also hate to memorize formulas by rote. I like probability the best, because it is closer to real life.

Both Students A and B were interested in drawing cartoons but disliked mathematics and had poor mathematical performance. During this study, they adapted their cartooning interests and skills to change their stereotypical impressions of mathematics and overcame their rejection of it through designing their own mathematical cartoons. According to the flow experiences of these two students, before designing their cartoons they believed it would be a challenging task and were confused about what they should design. However, both were willing to devote their free time to the task.

After reading the relevant information, Student A used her prior mathematical knowledge to consider applications in real life. She considered what cases might be suitable for design as a cartoon and integrated her own creative stories and characters to enrich her work. Similarly, after learning the basic concepts of calculus, Student B considered how to apply it in real life. When composing stories, she

started with simple dialogues, formed appealing and lively characters to attract readers, and then gradually introduced the concepts and formulas of calculus.

At this stage, after the two students had gained a preliminary understanding of mathematical formulas, they developed ideas and thought about how to combine mathematics and cartoons to produce stories, as well as how readers would accept the story content with mathematical formulas. By designing mathematical cartoon stories, they began to use their own independent thinking abilities.

Because these two students found mathematics difficult, they continually discussed mathematics with their teachers to modify their designs. During such discussions, they inspired each other to design stories and modify the statements in the mathematical formulas. Student A said that she was nervous in discussions with her mathematics teacher and was concerned about whether her mathematical statements were correct. She believed that her teacher could provide her with professional advice on how to express her ideas more clearly. If it was necessary to modify the figures, she needed to invent another plot. Student B reported that after discussions with her teacher, her mind was heavy with anxiety, but she looked forward to completing her work and was happy that the team members could learn from each other. As this group study was based on interdisciplinary cooperation, sharing, and exchange, it inspired her with new ideas to make her design more complete. At this stage, the students were clearly inspired by discussions with their mathematics teachers.

After designing her mathematical cartoon, Student A said that she better understood the content of the unit when she reread it. Student B stated that through her design she had learned the basic theorems of mathematics and could better distinguish its formulas.

The moods and experiences of flow in the two participants when drawing their mathematical cartoons were recorded. They started from their interest in drawing cartoons, independently designing their own mathematical cartoons and then receiving guidance from their teachers. Through training, they became more familiar with the content when they reread the unit corresponding to their mathematical cartoons, thereby improving their ability to understand mathematics.

Previous studies (Lee & Lin, 2015; Lee, 2015; Lee et al., 2016; Lee, 2017) explored the mathematics learning effectiveness of primary school students with low academic performance, noting that it was difficult for such students to draw graphs, think of examples, or summarize the course materials, thus reducing their confidence in learning.

This study therefore invited two female undergraduates who perceived their mathematics performance to be poor to join in the study group discussions and draw mathematical cartoons. Although both could draw cartoons featuring figures and objects, they failed to integrate mathematical principles and formulas and apply them to life through the dialogues. The study group therefore set aside 3 hours each week to instruct these two students using mathematical teaching materials. During the five instruction sessions, teachers gave examples of applying mathematics to daily life and asked them first to answer questions using pen and paper, then to express the mathematics they had learned in cartoons. This process was aimed at creating a user-friendly mathematics atmosphere for the two students to follow the study group's progress. Fig. 1 displays the mathematical cartoons drawn by the two students, indicating their improved understanding of mathematics. Both students believed that they understood mathematics better after reviewing it with their teachers' assistance.

(a) The first draft of the mathematical cartoon of Student A

(b) The improved version of the mathematical cartoon of Student A

(c) The first draft of the mathematical cartoon of Student B

(d) The improved version of the mathematical cartoon of Student A

Fig. 1 The mathematical cartoons completed by the two undergraduates

According to the two students' comments about the first drafts and improved versions, before drawing their mathematical cartoons they did not engage in discussions with their mathematical teachers, and therefore they could only design the characters and story outline without understanding how to integrate mathematical formulas into the dialogue. After consultation with their teachers, they better understood the mathematical formulas, enabling them to integrate these into the plots of their cartoons and thereby render their stories more complete.

This study explored the experience of flow during cartoon production, with results indicating that these two students with poor mathematics performance also had poor awareness of mathematical applications in real life. However, through the explanations of their teachers they gained an experience of flow in mathematical cartoon production, better understood the significance of mathematics in life, and thus changed their previous idea that mathematics could be studied but not applied to the real world. After drawing a cartoon for one unit, Student A felt a sense of achievement and asked if she could draw a sequel. Her experience of flow enhanced her sense of self-realization, thereby encouraging her to learn more challenging mathematical theories. Student B actively participated in study group discussions and looked for mathematical applications in real life, subsequently integrating them into her drawings. Therefore, through the flow experience of drawing mathematical cartoons, Students A and B overcame their resistance and achieved a greater understanding of mathematics.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The cartoon industry is growing rapidly on a global scale in both animated and still form. In many developed countries it has become a major industry with diverse possibilities. Cartoon readers range in age from children and adolescents to adults, and the audience is gradually expanding with the popularity of the Internet and multimedia. This study explored the production of mathematical cartoons and related experiences of flow. Through the flow experience of drawing mathematical cartoons, two students were challenged to study mathematics units that they did not understand well in order to overcome their resistance to learning mathematics and positively embracing it. Their independent mathematical thinking abilities were also improved. Moreover, their mathematical cartoons were worthy for adoption as teaching materials. Such hands-on experiences can motivate learners who are proficient at drawing cartoons to learn mathematics.

This study indicates that future mathematics textbooks should include cartoons. Cartoon animations could also be used as auxiliary materials to inspire creative teaching and learning, thereby encouraging students to think and actively apply mathematics in their daily lives.

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